

REINFORCING

Responsible tEerritories and Institutions eNable and
Foster Open Research and inClusive Innovation for
traNsitions Governance

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The REINFORCING project

- REINFORCING aims to become the Open and Responsible Research and Innovation (ORRI) **central point of knowledge and expertise** that supports territories and institutions in fostering Fair Transitions governance by aligning with societal values, needs and expectations.
- **REINFORCING One-Stop Source** platform acts as catalyzer of the quadruple-helix community, who will co-develop services, including policy recommendations.
- The project supports **institutional changes** aiming at responsible sustainability transitions through **96 grants** dedicated to boost institutions scaling up their ORRI capacities, and to support European regions experimenting with ORRI.
- In addition, **mentoring and matchmaking services** and training modules will be provided and a **Global ORRI Network** will be established.

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REINFORCING WORK PLAN STRUCTURE

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Two kinds of grants

ORRI BOOSTER

- 8-months projects, 4 calls, 12 proposals selected for each round.
- 1st topic: Open Innovation.

ORRI INCUBATORS

- 1-year projects, 3 calls, 8 proposals selected for each round.
- 1st topics: Balkans and Missions.
- Incubators are meant to support ORRI newcomers that need more time to experiment.

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The REINFORCING Consortium

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THANK YOU

www.reinforcing.eu

